

EXPLORING THE PERCEPTION AND PRACTICES OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract. Education for sustainable development (ESD) is one of the branches of sustainable development which is aimed at empowering imminent generations to tackle current environmental issues, however, it is confronting some challenges since there are some problems related to perception and practice of the notion “sustainable development”. The current work is dedicated to detecting how Uzbek and American teachers perceive the notion and whether they have tried to put it into practice or not. The materials were used questionnaire among Uzbek teachers and interned sources related to American teachers. The research is based on a descriptive method which analyzes sources and juxtapose the perception and practice of this notion.

Keywords: education for sustainable development (ESD), perception, practice, Uzbek teachers, American teachers.

INTRODUCTION

Due to current threats of environment, the new steps and changes are being taken to enable future generations to deal with this problem. Sustainable development for education is a science which teaches generations to be able to solve environmental problems by putting into practice of special methods like Resource Utilization as Per Carrying Capacity, 3 R (Reduce, Reuse, and Recycle Approach) and others. The term “sustainable development for education” is a well-researched topic, but it is not so much popular among Uzbek researchers and scholars. The current work is designed to identify the perception and practice of this term by Uzbek and American teachers. The sources are the questionnaire and internet materials.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

According to Foster:

sustainable development is:

- a process of making the emergent future ecologically sound and humanly habitable as it emerges, through the continuous responsive learning which is the human species’ most characteristic endowment
- a social learning process of improving the human condition
- a process which can be continued indefinitely without undermining itself

This way of thinking about sustainable development encapsulates the core role for learning as a collaborative and reflective process and captures the intergenerational dimension and the idea of environmental limits.

The recent researches related to sustainable development for education shows that there are three types of approaches were identified by Scott and Gough:

Type1 approaches admit that the issues humanity faces are essentially environmental, and can be understood through science and resolved by proper environmental and/or social actions

and technologies. It is assumed that learning leads to change once facts have been established and communicated.

Type 2 approaches presume that our central complications are social and/or political, and that these problems generate environmental symptoms. Such fundamental problems can be understood by means of anything from social-scientific analysis to an appeal to original knowledge.

Type 3 approaches suppose that what is (and can be) known in the present is not appropriate; chosen 'end-states' cannot be specified. This means that any learning must be open-ended. Type 3 approaches are important if the uncertainties and complexities inherent in how we live now are to lead to reflective social learning about how we might live in the future.

RESULTS

According to the questionnaire that was presented to Uzbek teachers who work at universities and institutions, most of the teachers have no idea or less information about education for sustainable development. On the other hand, some young teachers who would like to apply for foreign scholarships for European and Asian countries stated that they have some information about this theme, because it is considered as one of the most actual topics in researching and being able to get scholarships.

According to the results of next question, most of the participants of the questionnaire mentioned that they would like to have some trainings or seminars. Minority of teachers expressed less interest towards chances to have seminars or trainings to learn more about education for sustainable development.

The next question's results present that majority of teachers consider that teaching students with the help of sustainable development can be efficient to develop students' critical thinking and problem-solving skills. However, minority of teachers think that it does not help so much since learning must be based on major subjects rather than secondary subjects.

DISCUSSION

According to the results of internet sources, more than 6 universities have already started to teaching their students through ESD which shows that while Uzbek teachers have less information about this topic, American teachers have known this term for several years and have taught students through this method. All in all, it can be stated that Uzbekistan is also in the process of improving ESD and applying it in higher education.

CONCLUSION

Education for sustainable development (ESD) is UNESCO's education subdivision reply to the crucial and intense challenges the planet faces. The communal activities of human beings have moderated the earth's ecosystems so that our very survival seems in danger because of alters more complicated to reverse every day. The following work helps to detect how teachers perceive the term ESD and how they are applying it in higher education. Regarding to the results of the research, many teachers have less information about this notion while minority of teachers either have some information or have already started their research on this topic. Majority of teachers think that they need more trainings and seminars to know more about ESD. The results of another question shows that most participants of the questionnaire suppose that teaching students through ESD can be very efficient to develop important skills for real life. Overall, it can be concluded that teaching through ESD has already been commenced in America and Uzbekistan is also in the process of putting it into practice in upcoming years.

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